

Dihydroisocoumarins. Part VII. Effect of Substituents on the Lactonisation of 2-Carboxyphenethyl Alcohols

Shyam Kishore Prasad Sinha, D. N. Chaudhury, and Durgeshwari Prasad*

Isolation of stable 4-benzyloxy-2-carboxy-5-methoxyphenethyl alcohol (VI) and 4-allyloxy-2-carboxy-5-methoxyphenethyl alcohol (X) is reported and the effect of substituents on lactonisation of some 2-carboxyphenethyl alcohols to dihydroisocoumarins described.

During the course of the synthesis of 7-benzyloxy-3,4-dihydro-6-methoxyisocoumarin (I) by the route described earlier¹, the intermediate 4-benzyloxy-2-carboxy-5-methoxyphenethyl alcohol (VI) was isolated unexpectedly and found to be remarkably stable. It did not lactonise even on prolonged boiling with acidulated water. Such stability appears to be unusual, particularly in contrast to the instability of the intermediate 2-carboxyphenethyl alcohols (VII), (VIII), and (IX) which could not be isolated in the free state as these invariably lactonised, as soon as these were formed, to the corresponding dihydroisocoumarins (II)¹, (III)², and (IV)³. Another instance of a stable 2-carboxyphenethyl alcohol was further realised in the isolation of 4-allyloxy-2-carboxy-5-methoxyphenethyl alcohol (X) which lactonised, only when boiled with acidulated water, to the dihydroisocoumarin (V).

- | | |
|--|---|
| (I) : R = 6-OMe.-7-OCH ₂ Ph. | (VI) : R = 4-OCH ₂ Ph-5-OMe. |
| (II) : R = 7,8-di-OMe. | (VII) : R = 3,4-di-OMe. |
| (III) : R = 6,7-di-OMe. | (VIII) : R = 4,5-di-OMe. |
| (IV) : R = 5,8-di-OMe. | (IX) : R = 3,6-di-OMe. |
| (V) : R = 6-OMe.-7-OCH ₂ CH=CH ₂ . | (X) : R = 4-OCH ₂ CH=CH ₂ -5-OMe. |

In view of the foregoing observations it is thus reasonable to conclude that the ease with which 2-carboxyphenethyl alcohols form δ -lactones (dihydroisocoumarins) is dependent on the nature and position of the substituents in the benzene ring.

4-Benzyloxy-2-carboxy-5-methoxyphenethyl alcohol (VI) was prepared as follows. 4-Benzylxy-5-methoxy-2-nitrophenylacetic acid⁴ (XI) on treatment with diazomethane

*In part.

1. Banerjee and Chaudhury, *J. Org. Chem.* 1961, **26**, 4344.
2. Srivastava and Chaudhury, *this Journal*, 1961, **38**, 998.
3. Banerjee and Chaudhury, *ibid.*, 1962, **39**, 243.
4. Douglas and Gulland, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2893.

afforded methyl 4-benzyloxy-5-methoxy-2-nitrophenylacetate (XII). The latter was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride, followed by sodium dithionite, according to the procedure described earlier¹, to yield 2-amino-4-benzyloxy-5-methoxyphenethyl alcohol (XIII), isolated as its hydrochloride. After diazotisation of the amine hydrochloride, it was converted into the nitrile (which was not purified) and hydrolysed with sodium hydroxide solution. The alkaline solution, on acidification, did not yield the expected dihydroisocoumarin (I), but afforded a free acid, readily soluble in aqueous bicarbonate. It remained unchanged even on prolonged boiling with acidulated water. It was identified as 4-benzyloxy-2-carboxy-5-methoxyphenethyl alcohol (VI) since on sublimation *in vacuo* it lactonised to 7-benzyloxy-3,4-dihydro-6-methoxyisocoumarin (I), identical with an authentic specimen prepared earlier² by oxidation of 7-benzyloxy-6-methoxyisochroman. Esterification of the alcohol (VI) with diazomethane or with methyl iodide-potassium carbonate furnished the ester (XIV).

- (XI) : R = NO₂; R₁ = CH₂COOH.
 (XII) : R = NO₂; R₁ = CH₂COOMe.
 (XIII) : R = NH₂; R₁ = CH₂CH₂OH.
 (XIV) : R = COOMe; R₁ = CH₂CH₂OH.

In connection with some projected synthetic work, it became necessary to prepare 7-allyloxy-3,4-dihydro-6-methoxyisocoumarin (V). Interaction of allyl bromide and 3,4-dihydro-7-hydroxy-6-methoxyisocoumarin³ in presence of potassium carbonate in acetone afforded the dihydroisocoumarin (V), m.p. 94°, which was insoluble in aqueous bicarbonate. It dissolved in 2% sodium hydroxide solution, presumably due to opening of the δ -lactone ring. Acidification of the alkaline solution did not regenerate the dihydroisocoumarin (V), but furnished an acid, m.p. 125-26°, which was soluble in aqueous bicarbonate and after crystallisation from dilute methanol melted at 132°. The acid was proved to be 4-allyloxy-2-carboxy-5-methoxyphenethyl alcohol (X) since on boiling with acidulated water for half an hour it lactonised and was converted back to the dihydroisocoumarin (V).

*EXPERIMENTAL

Methyl 4-Benzyloxy-5-methoxy-2-nitrophenylacetate (XII).—A slurry of 4-benzyloxy-5-methoxy-2-nitrophenylacetic acid⁴ (24 g.) in ether was treated with an excess of ethereal diazomethane (from 30 g. of *N*-nitrosomethylurea). Next day, the ester (23.5 g.), m.p. 158-59°, which was insoluble in ether, was filtered. Two crystallisations from ethanol yielded the pure product (20.5 g.) as pale yellow needles, m. p. 164-65°. (Found: C, 61.4; H, 5.4; N, 4.3. C₁₇H₁₇O₆N requires C, 61.63; H, 5.1; N, 4.2%).

2-Amino-4-benzyloxy-5-methoxyphenethyl Alcohol (XIII).—A solution of the ester (XII) (6.5g.) in purified dry dioxane (150 ml) was added dropwise to a stirred suspension of LiAlH₄ (1.4 g.) in dry ether (100 ml), cooled to -15°, and left overnight at room temperature. The unchanged LiAlH₄ and the complex were decomposed by careful portionwise addi-

5. Prasad and Chaudhury, this *Journal*, 1962, 39, 672.

*All m.p.s. are uncorrected. Petroleum used had b.p. 60-80°.

tion of water (15 ml), followed by 2*N*-H₂SO₄ (100 ml) until the solution became clear. It was extracted with ether (75 ml × 5), the combined extract dried (K₂CO₃), and evaporated to a yellow solid residue, which was dissolved in methanol (100 ml). Sodium dithionite (15 g.) was added in instalments alternately with intermittent addition of water (150 ml) and the mixture refluxed for 1 hour. Most of the methanol was next distilled; the cooled aqueous solution was extracted with chloroform (50 ml × 5) and the extract was dried (Na₂SO₄) and concentrated under reduced pressure to a small bulk (ca. 5 ml). It was chilled in a freezing mixture and treated with ice-cooled dry ether (20 ml), saturated with dry HCl gas, when an almost colorless crystalline product (XIII) separated as its *hydrochloride* (4.5 g.), m. p. 197-98°. Two crystallisations from methanol-ether furnished the pure product as prismatic needles, m. p. 208-209° (decomp.). It could also be purified by sublimation *in vacuo* (bath temp. 180-90°/1 mm) in colorless prismatic needles, m. p. 208-209° (decomp.). (Found: C, 62.2; H, 6.6; N, 4.71. C₁₆H₁₀O₃NCl requires C, 62.0; H, 6.4; N, 4.53%).

4-Benzyl-oxy-2-carboxy-5-methoxyphenethyl Alcohol (VI).—A solution of the above amine hydrochloride (XIII) (2.7 g.), dissolved in HCl (21 ml, *d* 1.16) and water (49 ml) was diazotised with sodium nitrite (0.65 g.) in water (5.4 ml) at 0-2°. After neutralisation with sodium carbonate, the diazosolution was added to a solution containing potassium cyanide (2.1 g. in 15 ml water), nickel chloride (1.7 g. in 10 ml of water), and anhydrous sodium carbonate (0.53 g. in 10 ml of water) at 10° with stirring. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight at the room temperature. It was next heated at 70° for 1 hour, cooled, and extracted with chloroform (25 ml × 4). The combined extract was dried (Na₂SO₄) and the solvent evaporated to yield a dark solid. It was refluxed with aqueous KOH (150 ml, 10%) for 15 hours until evolution of ammonia had ceased. The filtered solution was extracted with chloroform (25 ml × 2) and the extract rejected. Acidification of the alkaline solution with HCl (conc.) precipitated a light brown solid (1.8 g.), m. p. 159-60°. Recrystallisations from ethyl acetate-light petroleum furnished the pure product as pale yellow needles, m. p. 178-79°. (Found: C, 67.2; H, 6.17. C₁₇H₁₃O₃ requires C, 67.5; H, 5.9%). It dissolved in aqueous bicarbonates and was reprecipitated on acidification. It remained unchanged when boiled with acidulated water for 1 hour.

4-Benzyl-oxy-2-methoxycarbonyl-5-methoxyphenethyl Alcohol (XIV).—(a). A cold solution of the alcohol (VI, 0.5 g.) in ether was treated with an excess ethereal diazomethane, prepared from 2 g. of *N*-nitrosomethylurea, and left overnight. Evaporation of the ether left a solid residue which on recrystallisation from ethyl acetate-petroleum furnished the pure compound (0.4 g.) as pale yellow, rhombic plates, m. p. 128-29°. (Found: C, 68.62; H, 5.96. C₁₈H₁₅O₃ requires C, 68.3; H, 6.3%).

(b). A solution of the alcohol (VI, 0.5 g.) in pure dry acetone (25 ml), methyl iodide (1 ml), and freshly ignited potassium carbonate (2 g.) were refluxed for 8 hours. The solution was filtered and evaporated to a solid residue. Recrystallisations from ethyl acetate-petroleum provided the pure ester (XIV) (0.35 g.), m. p. 129°, undepressed on admixture with the specimen prepared by method (a).

7-Benzyl-oxy-3,4-dihydro-6-methoxyisocoumarin (I).—The alcohol (VI, 0.25 g.) was sublimed *in vacuo* (bath temp. 140-50°/6 mm) and the sublimate after one crystallisation from ethyl acetate-petroleum afforded the pure isocoumarin (I) as pale yellow shining plates (0.17 g.), m. p. 126°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen prepared earlier² by a different route.

*7-*Allyloxy-3,4-dihydro-6-methoxyisocoumarin* (V).—A mixture of 3,4-dihydro-7-hydroxy-6-methoxyisocoumarin³ (2.2 g.), freshly distilled allyl bromide (2 ml), and anhydrous potassium carbonate (3 g.) in dry acetone (25 ml) was refluxed for 16 hours. The solid was filtered and washed several times with dry acetone. The washings and the filtrate were combined and evaporated to provide a brown crystalline solid (2.6 g.). It was washed thrice with petroleum to remove the unchanged allyl bromide and then crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum to afford the isocoumarin (V; 2.3 g.) as fine colorless needles, m.p. 94° (Found: C, 66.94; H, 6.27. $C_{15}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 66.66; H, 5.98%).

*4-*Allyloxy-2-carboxy-3-methoxyphenethyl Alcohol* (X).—The foregoing compound (V, 0.5 g.) was stirred with aqueous 20% NaOH solution (15 ml) at room temperature for 1 hour, when a clear solution was obtained. On acidification, a white precipitate, m.p. 125-26°, was obtained which was collected. Recrystallisation from dilute methanol furnished the pure alcohol (0.4 g.) as colorless, felted needles, m.p. 132°. (Found: C, 61.6; H, 6.58. $C_{15}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 61.9; H, 6.3%). It dissolved in aqueous bicarbonate and was reprecipitated on acidification. On boiling for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. with acidulated water, it was converted into the dihydroisocoumarin (V); m. p. and mixed m. p. 94°.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
L. S. COLLEGE, BIHAR UNIVERSITY,
MUZAFFARPUR.

Received January 2, 1963.